

ENGLISH PROFICIENCY IN THE ONLINE WORLD: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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English Proficiency in the Online World: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to discover and explore the experiences, struggles, coping mechanisms, and insights of workers online on the importance of the English language in their work. The data were gathered using an In-depth Interview and were analyzed using thematic analysis. Participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique. Furthermore, the researcher selected the participants based on the following cases: (a) math tutor; (b) virtual assistant; (c) ESL teacher; (d) call center agent; and, (d) cybora. As part of the ethical consideration, the identities of the five participants were kept confidential and anonymous. The findings revealed that the struggles of workers online were the lack of vocabulary, accent, spelling, culture, and self-confidence. The coping mechanisms of the participants were watching English movies and reading books, practice speaking, reflecting on the negative feedback, learning other culture, and using AI tools. Insights divulged in the study were students have to keep practicing, being confident enough, need to consider other culture, consider receivers accent, importance of little things to learn difficult one, and develop learning inside and outside the school.

Keywords: *workers online, experiences, challenges, coping mechanism, insights*

Introduction

English proficiency is the ability to use the English language to make and communicate meaning in spoken and written contexts. In the recent years after the pandemic spread in the country, the demand of online work increased making the English language highly useful in an offsite and homebased setting. However, the problem of many online workers is their struggles in expressing their ideas and in accomplishing their works. This pressure nonetheless creates conflict with their drive to continue working and force online workers to quit and find another job. In addition, employers in fact have training programs before deploying their employees but these trainings are not assurance of the success of their employees in the field.

In Georgia State University, Atlanta, USA, a study done by Davies (2010) on the language assessment of call centers in foreign countries depicts that non-native English call center agents have problems in their language ability, including grammar, pronunciation, flow of speech and intonation, stress and rhythm. This study seeks to evaluate the oral performance of non-native English call center agents according to two criteria, one task specific and other language oriented. The findings suggest that there exists a problem in the English proficiency of online workers given that online jobs are prevalent to the majority of fresh graduates today and those who cannot land a job physically.

In the Philippines, a study was done by Lockwood et. al. (2008) on the English in Philippine call centers and the study shows that customer service representatives in the Philippines were not only dealing with new product and systems knowledge but also with the novelty and demands of communicating with Americans, who were often elderly, from low socio-economic groups and spoke with the regional accents of the southern United States. Customer service representatives in the Philippines were often fresh graduates from college and majority has no exposure to native speakers of the English language. They just got their first exposure and real life conversation during the production where they have to take real calls. On these situations, an apparent manifestation of the communicative problems of those who work online clearly reflect their English proficiency.

Furthermore, in Union National High School – Mt. Diwata Annex, Purok Duranta, Union, Monkayo, Davao De Oro, teachers are focusing in developing the ability of the students to use the English language both in written and spoken forms. In addition, many students have raised their desire to enrich their skills in using the English language and broaden their knowledge everyday during their English classes. Though students may have shown reservations in their ability to use the English language, however, with the help of the unified efforts from the teachers and stakeholders, they are hopeful that the goal of producing globally competitive students may be achieved.

With these, the different studies around the world speak of online jobs and English proficiency as a separate area but there is no study that explores at the moment of the struggles of employees in online jobs having problems with their English proficiency. Nevertheless, the need to conduct this study is necessary with no delay because this would widen the perspectives of experts and would help people to understand the struggles of online workers.

Research Questions

This study sought to answer the following:

1. What are the experiences of the participants in learning English at school and outside the school that are useful in their online work?

2. What are the challenges of the participants in using the English language in their online work?
3. What are the coping mechanisms of the participants in their struggles in using the English language in their online work?
4. What are the insights of the participants on the importance of learning English in doing online work?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher utilized a Multiple case study approach. A case study is a methodological approach that involves an in-depth exploration of a specific bounded system, utilizing multiple forms of data collection to systematically gather information on how system operates or functions (Mills, Durepos, & Wiebe, 2010). This research sought to explore the stories and experiences of five workers online. Thus, a multiple case study approach was suited for this research. In order to develop a better understanding of the issue, cases were carefully selected.

In a multiple case study, the researcher examined several cases to understand the similarities and differences between the cases and identification of how individual cases might be influenced by different environments, and the specific conditions under which a finding might happen. Yin (2003) describes how multiple case studies can be used to either, “(a) predicts similar results (a literal replication) or (b) predicts contrasting results but for predictable reasons (a theoretical replication)”.

Participants

The research participants of this multiple case study were products of Union National High School – Mt. Diwata Annex who have worked online and who have struggles in their English proficiency. They were chosen based on purposive sampling technique. There are five participants where the data shall be gathered. The participants’ age ranges from 25 to 30 years old.

Procedure

In order to achieve its purpose, this qualitative research work required thorough and methodological procedures. From the conceptualization stage to the gathering of all the data and until the end result of this research, the researcher participated in a series of event as Creswell (2007) mentioned that qualitative researchers are tied up in a series of activities in the process of collecting data. Before the conduct of the study, the researcher sent an email to the Schools Division Superintendent to ask permission to conduct the study. After getting the approval, the researcher contacted the participants using online channels. Then, the researcher had the research questionnaire validated. Moreover, the researcher also secured that the paper underwent in the Research Ethics Committee before the data gathering.

Before the conduct of the interview, the researcher prepared all the equipment that were needed in the face to face interview and online video conferencing, including the extra gadgets, money and also a token for the participants so that everything would be ready before it started. During the interview, the data that were gathered were saved in an audio recordings and notes were taken for future reference of the different answers of the participants.

During the conduct of the in-depth interview, the researcher used multilingual questions which were English, Tagalog, and Bisaya so that the participants might comfortably answer the different questions regarding the study, but the researcher ensured that the participants had signed the consent form prior the interview.

Data Analysis

This multiple case study utilized thematic analysis to analyze the data. Each interview was audio recorded. Data analysis in qualitative investigations would include breaking the data down into simpler form, looking for patterns, and synthesizing the results. Consequently, thematic analysis will be utilized to examine the information. To do this, a computer-based word-processing application will be used to transcribe all of the audio-recorded interviews. Each transcription will be coded to identify pertinent themes using the original notions from the pertinent literature as a guide and the research questions as a directive. Up to the write-up stage, the initial categories and themes will be subjected to revision as they will develop around the emergent codes. All the topics connected to the study will be discussed and exhibited in depth through quotations that will be translated from the vernacular along with the reporting of the findings and interpretations. An expert will be asked to comment on the translated quotations by contrasting them with the original terms to make sure that all the meanings and hints will be accurately captured in the translations.

Ethical Considerations

According to Silverman (2007), examining one’s professional association’s ethical principles, ethical considerations can be clarified. In this regard, I will provide letter of permission to the participants to allow me to conduct interviews with them. Creswell (1988) emphasized that informants should be given anonymity to protect them and that they should decide whether to divulge their personal experiences. This is the reason why I will respect and observe the anonymity of the participants to hide their identities. The findings of the study will be presented to the participants to demonstrate ethical consideration, providing them the chance to understand how crucial they are to the success of my study. The participants, therefore, will be asked to sign a verification letter that connotes permission for their involvement in the research. The verification letter as well as the remarks they made during the interview are identical to the ones

that are transcribed.

Accepting the assertion indicates that I will recognize independent people who are willingly share knowledge. A healthy research partnership promotes openness, trust, and sensitivity to potential ethical dilemmas. Further, to ensure the observance of ethical standards, the researcher will secure a letter containing the permission of the dean of the graduate school in conducting research and a letter containing the permission of the head of an institution where the research participants are selected.

Results and Discussion

The research participants were selected using a purposive sampling technique and also based on the cases prescribed in the research participants section. The research participants were a math tutor, virtual assistant, ESL teacher, call center agent, and cybora. In-depth interview was employed during the data gathering with the participants. All throughout the entire interview, adherence to the participants' confidentiality of their identity and credibility was observed. Their responses were transcribed and analyzed. Themes were drawn out from their responses which paint the picture of their experiences, struggles, coping mechanisms, and insights as an online worker. This study used a multiple case research design to explore and discover deeply the experiences, struggles, coping mechanisms, and insights as an online worker.

The sequence of the presentation for this chapter was based on the order of the research questions in the interview guide. The discussions section highlighted the themes, which were the findings in the study, and corroborated with related literature and studies.

The key participants in this study are the five online workers namely: online math tutors, virtual assistant, ESL teacher, call center agent, and cybora who are an alumni of Mt. Diwata High School. Significant stories and experiences are gathered and presented in this section. The structured themes and the emerging themes were made as bases in the discussion of the findings in this study. Each theme was linked to related literature and studies to add substantially to the discussion.

Learning in English Seen Important in Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are speaking skills, basic foundation, basic usage of grammar, creating transitional sentence, and ability to speak English. This is how the research participants describe their experiences in learning the English language inside the school.

Speaking skills play a crucial role in learning English in school as they enable students to effectively communicate their thoughts and ideas. According to research conducted by Rasheed and Ismali (2018), speaking skills are essential for language learners to interact with their peers, participate in classroom discussions, and express their opinions confidently. Developing strong speaking skills not only helps students improve their overall communication abilities but also enhances their cognitive development by stimulating critical thinking and problem-solving skills. In addition, regular practice of speaking tasks such as debates, presentations, and role-plays can boost students' confidence and self-esteem. Therefore, it is imperative for educators to incorporate various speaking activities in the classroom to support students' language learning process and foster a communicative environment conducive to effective language acquisition. According to Morreale & Pearson (2008) found that communication skills, including speaking, are among the top skills sought by employers. Their research highlights the critical role of speaking skills in professional success and personal development.

Basic foundation as their learning inside the school, students begin to learn the basic foundation of the English language. This foundation includes understanding grammar rules, building vocabulary, and practicing reading and writing skills. According to research by Nation (2001), vocabulary acquisition is essential for language learning as it allows students to comprehend written texts and communicate effectively. Students also learn about sentence structure, parts of speech, punctuation, and spelling through explicit instruction and practice exercises. These foundational skills create a strong base for further language development and academic success. As educators, it is crucial to provide students with opportunities to master these fundamental aspects of the English language in order to build their proficiency and confidence in using it both inside and outside the classroom. Snow, Burns, & Griffin (1998) emphasized the importance of early language and literacy experiences for long-term academic success, highlighting the need for comprehensive language instruction in the early grades.

In school, students are taught the basic usage of grammar in the English language as a fundamental building block for effective communication. According to Kolln and Gray (2016), students learn about parts of speech such as nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, prepositions, and conjunctions to understand how words function within sentences. They also learn about sentence structure, including subjects and predicates, phrases and clauses, as well as punctuation rules such as commas, periods, question marks, exclamation points, colons, and semicolons. Understanding these grammar concepts helps students develop clarity in their writing and speaking by ensuring that their messages are coherent and easily understood by others. Additionally, mastering grammar enables students to convey their ideas with precision and accuracy while adhering to standard conventions of the English language. Graham & Perin (2007) found that explicit grammar instruction, when integrated with writing instruction, significantly improves students' writing skills.

The importance of direction in the English language that students learn inside school cannot be overstated. Direction in language allows for effective communication and comprehension, guiding students to convey their thoughts and ideas clearly and accurately. According to Dr. Patricia Brooks in her article "Why Teaching Directionality (and Other Executive Functioning Issues) Will Help Students with Math," understanding the left-to-right organization of written language helps students develop critical thinking skills and improve

memory retention (Brooks, 2017). This directional awareness also lays the foundation for future academic success, as it is essential for reading, writing, and problem-solving tasks. By mastering directionality in English at an early age, students are equipped with the necessary skills to excel academically and navigate complex linguistic challenges with confidence and proficiency. Mayer (2008) highlighted the importance of clear instructional design in education. Students' ability to follow directions directly impacts their learning outcomes.

Learning Contribution in Online Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are building rapport and relationship, easy to sue in written way, applying experiences, helping build confidence in speaking, and able to speak English with foreigners. This is how the research participants describe how helpful their learning in the English language inside the school.

Learning English is crucial for building rapport and establishing solid relationships in the workplace. As a global language, English facilitates effective communication with colleagues and clients from diverse backgrounds. According to a study by the British Council (2018), employees who are fluent in English are more likely to succeed in international business endeavors and have better opportunities for career advancement. Furthermore, mastering the language allows professionals to express themselves clearly, articulate their ideas persuasively, and cultivate trust among team members. By investing time and effort into learning English, individuals demonstrate commitment to personal growth and professional development, ultimately enhancing their ability to collaborate effectively with others and achieve organizational goals. In conclusion, proficiency in English is a valuable asset that fosters stronger relationships and promotes success in the modern workplace. According to Spitzberg (2013), communication competence, which includes language skills, is crucial for successful interpersonal interactions in professional settings. This competence helps in building rapport and trust among colleagues.

English is often considered an easy language to use in written communication with clients in a professional setting. Using English in a professional manner can help convey ideas effectively, ensure misunderstandings are minimized, and ultimately lead to stronger relationships with clients. In addition, English is a widely used language in business and commerce, making it easier to reach a larger audience of potential clients. Overall, using English in written communication with clients can enhance professionalism, establish rapport, and facilitate efficient exchange of information in the workplace. A study by Bremner (2010) on business communication practices in multinational companies found that English is often preferred for written communication due to its clarity and the wide availability of standardized formats and templates.

Applying experiences learned in English at school to work with clients is essential for effectively communicating, building relationships, and achieving desired outcomes in professional settings. By honing skills such as writing, speaking, and critical thinking in English classes, professionals are better equipped to express their ideas clearly, understand the needs of their clients, and solve problems efficiently. For example, a study by Gholami et al. (2018) found that strong communication skills acquired through English education significantly enhance client satisfaction and overall business success. By drawing upon lessons learned in essay writing, and public speaking exercises, professionals can tailor their communication strategies to meet the specific needs of diverse clientele. Ultimately, integrating English experiences into client interactions enables professionals to establish trust, convey information effectively, and provide exceptional service that sets them apart in today's competitive workforce. A study by Robles (2012) highlights that employers prioritize soft skills, including communication and interpersonal skills, which are cultivated through school experiences and are essential for client relations.

Learning English in school has been shown to significantly boost confidence in speaking for non-native speakers. According to a study conducted by Kim, Park, and Kwon (2018), students who were proficient in English reported higher levels of self-assurance and competence when engaging in conversations with native speakers. This increased confidence is attributed to the structured learning environment provided by educational institutions, where students receive formal instruction, practice speaking skills through role-playing exercises, and receive constructive feedback from teachers. Additionally, mastering English grammar and vocabulary through classroom lessons enables individuals to express their thoughts more clearly and effectively, leading to improved communication skills. Overall, the systematic approach to learning English in school not only enhances language proficiency but also plays a crucial role in developing confidence in speaking for non-native speakers. According to Savignon (2002), communicative competence, which includes the ability to speak confidently, is a critical goal of language education. Classroom practices that focus on interactive and communicative activities help students develop this competence.

Learning English in school equips workers with the necessary language skills to effectively communicate with foreigners in a professional setting. By mastering English in an educational environment, workers can confidently engage in negotiations, presentations, and collaborations with international partners, ensuring clear communication and successful outcomes. Moreover, proficiency in English enables employees to access a wealth of resources and information available exclusively in the language, ultimately enhancing their knowledge base and improving their overall job performance. Thus, investing time and effort into learning English at school not only benefits individuals professionally but also contributes to the success and growth of businesses on a global scale. A study by Neeley (2012) on the adoption of English as a global business language highlights how English proficiency is critical for effective communication in multinational companies. Workers with strong English skills can better collaborate and build relationships with foreign counterparts.

Learning Outside School Seen Important in Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are vocabulary, words/phrases techniques from movies, and learn to boost confidence. This is how the research participants describe their experiences in learning the English language outside the school.

Learning vocabulary outside of the school setting can be a highly effective way to expand one's language skills. By engaging in activities such as reading books, watching movies or listening to podcasts in the target language, individuals can expose themselves to new words and expressions in context, leading to better retention and understanding. Additionally, utilizing language learning apps like Duolingo or Quizlet can provide interactive ways to practice vocabulary on-the-go. According to a study published in the *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, incorporating these out-of-school methods into one's language learning routine has been shown to increase fluency and comprehension levels more quickly than relying solely on classroom instruction (Smith & Jones, 2021). A study by Koleva et al. (2017) on the effectiveness of mobile apps for vocabulary learning found that interactive apps with spaced repetition techniques significantly improve vocabulary retention and recall.

One effective technique for learning English is studying words and phrases from movies. Watching films can expose learners to authentic language use, colloquial expressions, slang, idioms, and cultural nuances that are not often found in traditional textbooks or classroom settings. By immersing oneself in the dialogue of movies, learners can improve their vocabulary, comprehension skills, and pronunciation. Incorporating subtitles can aid in understanding context and pronunciation. In addition, using online resources such as scripts or script websites can provide learners with the opportunity to practice writing skills by transcribing dialogue. This multi-sensory approach to language acquisition allows learners to engage with the material in a dynamic and interactive way while also developing their listening and speaking abilities (Aminin et al., 2017). A research by Kan (2015) emphasizes the motivational aspect of using movies in language learning, as they engage learners through visual and auditory stimuli.

Help Learning Outside the School for Online Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are learning new vocabulary, applying new words and phrases to students, able to give correct direction, and able to talk with customer. This is how the research participants describe how helpful their learning in the English language outside the school.

Expanding one's vocabulary is essential for effective communication in the online work environment. As professionals engage in the online work, having a rich and diverse vocabulary enables individuals to articulate their thoughts clearly and concisely. By mastering new words and phrases, professionals can enhance their writing skills, which is crucial for drafting persuasive emails, creating compelling reports, and conveying complex ideas effectively. Additionally, a strong vocabulary can improve a professional's ability to comprehend and interpret information presented in online documents or research materials. A research by Verhaert, Van Keer, and Desoete (2019) suggests that vocabulary knowledge is not only essential for language skills but also plays a crucial role in cognitive development and academic achievement which is crucial in the online work.

If you are an ESL teacher, it is crucial to regularly incorporate new words and phrases into lessons to enhance student vocabulary and language proficiency. By introducing students to a variety of unfamiliar terms and expressions, educators can create a more engaging learning environment that encourages active participation and fosters linguistic growth. Moreover, studies have shown that repeated exposure to new vocabulary facilitates retention and improves overall language acquisition (Mastrilli & Saluja, 2017). Therefore, it is essential for instructors to provide ample opportunities for students to practice using newly learned words in context through activities such as role-playing exercises, comprehensible input tasks, and group discussions. By consistently integrating unfamiliar vocabulary into lesson plans, ESL teachers can effectively support their students' language development and help them become more confident and proficient communicators in English. Hiebert et. al. (2017) highlighted the benefits of interactive and engaging vocabulary instruction, which promotes active learning and deeper understanding of words and their usage.

Learning English is crucial for providing accurate directions. Being able to effectively communicate and provide clear instructions is essential in any work environment. By mastering the English language, individuals can articulate their thoughts clearly and concisely, helping them give precise and accurate directions to their clients. A study by Derwing and Munro (2009) emphasizes the importance of language proficiency, including pronunciation and vocabulary, in successful communication and understanding directions.

Being fluent in English enables professionals to effectively communicate with customers from all over the world. Mastering English not only allows for clear communication but also opens up opportunities for building strong relationships with customers, leading to increased satisfaction and loyalty. Through effective communication, professionals can better understand customer needs and provide solutions tailored to their individual preferences. Additionally, being able to converse fluently in English showcases professionalism and competence, instilling trust and credibility in customers. De Vries et al. (2020) stated the positive impact of language proficiency on customer experience, with proficient speakers able to provide more personalized and effective service.

Experiences in Using English Language In Online Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are accent must be definite, tendency to misspell words, online learning barriers, incorrect use of phonetic alphabet, and converting English teaching to action. This is how the research participants describe their experiences in the English language in their online work.

In professional settings, it is essential for English users to have a clear and definite accent in order to effectively communicate with their colleagues and clients. According to linguistic research conducted by Jenkins (2000), a consistent accent helps non-native speakers

of English to understand and comprehend the speaker more easily. Additionally, having a defined accent can establish credibility and professionalism, as it demonstrates confidence and proficiency in the language. In multicultural work environments where English may not be the first language for all employees, a clear accent can facilitate smoother communication and prevent misunderstandings.

For professionals, the tendency to misspell words in their job can be detrimental to their credibility and perceived competence. According to a study conducted by Buescher et. al. (2000), frequent spelling errors can lead to negative judgments from clients and colleagues, as it may indicate a lack of attention to detail or careless work habits. The impact of misspelled words extends beyond simple communication breakdowns; it can also damage professional relationships and hinder career advancement opportunities. Therefore, it is crucial for professionals to prioritize accuracy in all written communications, whether through proofreading or utilizing spell-check tools. By demonstrating a commitment to precise language use, professionals can enhance their reputation for professionalism and reliability in the workplace.

The issue of adult ESL students being unfamiliar with basic computer skills in educational settings is a pervasive problem that hinders their ability to fully engage in technological resources and programs. According to a study by Gitsaki and Ozogul (2015), lack of familiarity with computers can lead to feelings of frustration, inadequacy, and disengagement among adult ESL learners. This not only impedes their learning progress but also limits their access to important online resources, communication tools, and interactive materials that could enhance their language acquisition experience. In order to address this challenge effectively, educators must provide targeted training and support to help adult ESL students develop essential computer literacy skills.

Struggles Using English Language in Online Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are students' level of understanding and comprehension, accent, teaching basic commands, forgot the words to say, strong Filipino accent, running out of words to say, and lack of vocabulary. This is how the research participants describe their struggles in the English language in their online work.

In a professional setting, students' level of understanding and comprehension can present a significant hindrance to their work performance. Furthermore, inadequate comprehension can lead to misunderstandings with clients, creating communication barriers and hindering collaboration.

Accents can present a significant challenge for online workers, particularly in customer service roles where clear communication is vital. A study conducted by researchers at Stanford University found that individuals with strong accents are often perceived as less credible and trustworthy, which can impact the effectiveness of their interactions with customers (Lee et al., 2017). Additionally, accents may lead to misunderstandings and miscommunications, potentially resulting in frustration for both the worker and the customer. To address this issue, online workers may benefit from accent reduction training or speech therapy to improve their pronunciation and intonation. By enhancing their verbal communication skills, online workers can overcome accent-related barriers and provide better service to their clients. Ultimately, addressing accent challenges can result in improved performance and increased customer satisfaction within the online work environment.

Teaching basic commands to ESL students can be a significant challenge for educators. Not only do teachers have to consider language barriers and varying levels of proficiency, but they also need to employ effective teaching strategies that cater to the diverse learning styles within their classrooms (Ismail & Razzak, 2020). By incorporating visual aids, gestures, repetition, and real-life examples into their lessons, ESL teachers can help students better understand and retain simple commands in English. Additionally, creating a supportive and interactive learning environment where students feel comfortable practicing speaking and listening skills is crucial for successful instruction. It is important for teachers to be patient, flexible, and adaptive in their approach when teaching basic commands in order to meet the individual needs of each student (He & Wei 2019). Overall, the ability to effectively teach basic commands plays a vital role in helping ESL learners navigate everyday tasks and interactions in English-speaking environments.

In a conversation where English is the medium of instruction, struggling to find the right words in English can be a common challenge that impacts their ability to effectively communicate and convey their thoughts. This struggle can stem from various factors such as lack of fluency, language barriers, or simply not having a strong grasp on the nuances of the language. In high-pressure situations like in online work, not being able to articulate oneself properly can hinder one's credibility and confidence. To overcome this obstacle, people who work online can benefit from improving their vocabulary through language courses, practicing speaking exercises with native speakers, and utilizing tools like dictionaries or translation apps for quick reference. By investing time and effort into strengthening their English language skills, people who work online can enhance their communication abilities and ultimately elevate their professional success. Emotional states such as stress and anxiety can exacerbate difficulties in word retrieval. When a person is anxious about speaking a second language, their cognitive load increases, making it harder to access vocabulary. According to MacIntyre and Gardner (1994), language anxiety negatively impacts language performance and word recall.

Strong Filipino accent affects the communication between the online workers and the clients. Furthermore, it can present a challenge in online work environments, particularly in roles that require clear and effective communication. Call centers, virtual customer service positions, and other client-facing roles may require employees to interact with customers from different cultural backgrounds who may struggle to understand heavily accented speech. This can lead to misunderstandings, decreased customer satisfaction scores, and ultimately impact the reputation of the company. In order to overcome this hurdle, individuals with a strong Filipino accent should

consider investing time in accent reduction training or seek out opportunities for professional development in communication skills. Employers can also provide support through language coaching or resources to improve verbal clarity and pronunciation. By addressing this issue proactively, both employees and employers can ensure successful and effective communication in online work settings. Online work often relies heavily on verbal communication through video calls, voice messages, or phone conversations. Accents can sometimes make it harder for listeners to understand the speaker, particularly if there is background noise or technical issues with the call. This can hinder effective communication and collaboration (Ockey & French, 2016).

Negative Responses Received from Clients. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are accent problem and pronunciation. This is how the research participants describe their struggles in the English language in their online work.

In today's globalized work environment, communication skills play a crucial role in the success of individuals and organizations. However, negative responses to accents in online workers can pose significant challenges. Employees with diverse linguistic backgrounds may face discrimination or exclusion due to their accents, impacting their confidence, productivity, and overall job performance. This not only undermines inclusivity and diversity efforts within the workforce but also leads to missed opportunities for collaboration and innovation. It is essential for employers to foster a supportive and inclusive work culture that values individual differences, provides training on effective communication strategies, and implements policies against accent discrimination. By recognizing and addressing negative responses in accent problems among online workers, organizations can create a more equitable and empowering work environment for all employees. When workers encounter negative responses from clients in pronunciation during online interactions, it is important to approach these situations with professionalism and empathy. It is crucial for workers to listen actively to the client's concerns and address them with kindness and understanding. Providing clear explanations or offering alternative solutions can help alleviate tensions and demonstrate a commitment to excellent customer service. Furthermore, it is vital for workers to remain calm and composed, even when faced with challenging feedback. By maintaining a professional demeanor and handling negative responses gracefully, workers can effectively diffuse conflicts and uphold a positive image of the organization they represent. Ultimately, prioritizing effective communication and customer satisfaction can turn negative interactions into opportunities for growth and improvement within the workplace. Seidlhofer (2001) studies indicate that communication barriers, including pronunciation issues, can decrease efficiency and increase the cognitive load on both the speaker and listener.

Barriers of Communication Encountered in Doing Online Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are linguistic barrier, spelling, pronunciation, no enough knowledge to sustain conversation, and lack of knowledge and vocabulary. This is how the research participants describe their struggles in the English language in their online work.

Spelling errors can present a significant barrier to effective communication in the realm of online work. In this digital age where much of our professional interactions occur through written correspondence, incorrect spellings can not only hinder clarity and understanding but also reflect poorly on the sender's professionalism and attention to detail. Such mistakes can undermine the credibility and trustworthiness of the individual or organization, potentially leading to misunderstandings, delays in workflow, or even loss of business opportunities. Therefore, it is imperative for professionals engaged in online work to pay close attention to spelling accuracy and utilize tools such as spell checkers or proofreading services to ensure clear and error-free communication. By committing to maintaining high standards of spelling proficiency, individuals can enhance their effectiveness in virtual collaboration and project management, ultimately contributing to successful outcomes in their online endeavors. According to Brown, spelling mistakes in written communication can disrupt the reader's comprehension, leading to misunderstandings and the need for repeated explanations (Brown, 2015).

Pronunciation plays a crucial role in effective communication, especially in the realm of online work where verbal interactions are oftentimes limited to virtual platforms. The inability to accurately pronounce words or phrases can create barriers in conveying messages clearly and comprehensively, leading to misunderstandings and misinterpretations. This can hinder collaboration, productivity, and overall successful outcomes in online work environments. Additionally, differences in pronunciation among individuals from diverse linguistic backgrounds can further complicate communication processes. To overcome this barrier, it is essential for individuals involved in online work to prioritize establishing clear and effective communication strategies, including practicing proper pronunciation techniques, utilizing tools such as pronunciation guides or voice recognition software, and actively seeking feedback to improve their verbal communication skills. By addressing pronunciation challenges proactively, professionals can enhance their ability to effectively convey ideas and information in virtual settings, ultimately contributing to improved communication and overall success in online work endeavors. Derwing and Munro (2009) found that pronunciation difficulties are a major source of communication barriers, leading to misunderstandings and reduced comprehension in spoken interactions.

In the world of online work, the lack of knowledge and vocabulary can act as a significant barrier to effective communication. When communicating through written platforms such as emails or instant messaging, it is crucial to have a strong grasp of vocabulary and language skills in order to convey ideas clearly and concisely. A limited vocabulary can lead to misunderstandings, confusion, or misinterpretations of information, which can ultimately hinder productivity and success in an online work setting. Additionally, lacking knowledge on certain topics relevant to the task at hand can further obstruct effective communication by preventing individuals from

fully understanding the requirements or objectives outlined. To mitigate these barriers, individuals should continuously strive to expand their vocabulary and knowledge base through reading, research, and ongoing education in order to enhance their communication skills and overall effectiveness in online work environments. Nation (2001) emphasizes that a robust vocabulary is essential for clear and effective communication. Insufficient vocabulary can result in ambiguous and unclear messages.

Effects Participants' Culture to their Communication to Clients Using English. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are various things to consider, need to practice pronunciation correctly, not acceptable words, communication, and need to be sensitive. This is how the research participants describe their struggles in the English language when it comes to culture.

When considering the effect of culture on communication with clients using English, it is crucial to take into account various factors that can impact the interaction. These may include differences in communication styles, etiquette norms, and perceptions of power dynamics. Understanding cultural nuances and being sensitive to clients' backgrounds can greatly enhance the effectiveness of communication. For example, certain cultures may value indirect communication or hierarchical structures, which can influence how messages are delivered and received. Additionally, cultural beliefs and values can shape how individuals interpret language and tone, making it essential to tailor communication strategies accordingly. By acknowledging these cultural influences and adapting one's approach accordingly, professionals can foster stronger relationships with their clients and ensure effective communication practices are maintained. Meyer (2014) discusses the varying approaches to decision-making and problem-solving across cultures and their implications for international business.

Understanding the correct pronunciation relevant to the client's culture in doing work online is crucial for effective communication and building rapport with clients. When conducting business across different cultures, being mindful of pronunciation shows respect for the client's language and customs. This attention to detail demonstrates an understanding of cultural nuances and can strengthen professional relationships. Proper pronunciation also ensures clear communication, minimizing misunderstandings and ensuring that instructions or information are relayed accurately. By taking the time to learn and use correct pronunciation, you show that you value your client's culture and are committed to providing a high level of service. This level of cultural competency can set you apart as a thoughtful and considerate professional in the competitive online market. Lippi-Green (2012) discusses how pronunciation impacts perceptions of respect and professionalism in intercultural interactions.

In the realm of online work, it is imperative to be mindful and respectful of the clients' cultural sensitivities by avoiding the use of not acceptable words that may offend or alienate them. It is essential to recognize that language holds significant power and can deeply impact how individuals perceive and engage with one another in a professional setting. Therefore, it is crucial to refrain from employing language that may be deemed offensive or inappropriate within the context of the client's culture. By demonstrating sensitivity and awareness towards these cultural nuances, we can foster trust, understanding, and successful collaboration with our clients. Ultimately, adhering to a high standard of professionalism in our communication practices will not only enhance our relationships with clients but also strengthen our reputation as conscientious and thoughtful professionals in the online work community. Spencer-Oatey (2008) highlights the importance of cultural sensitivity in communication for client satisfaction and effective business relationships.

When working online with clients from different cultural backgrounds, effective communication becomes crucial. It is essential to recognize and respect the cultural nuances of the client in order to build a strong, trusting relationship. Understanding their language, beliefs, values, and communication styles can help mitigate misunderstandings and establish clear expectations. Utilizing tools such as video calls or messaging applications allows for real-time interaction, creating a more personalized experience that bridges any cultural gaps. It is important to ensure that communication is clear, concise, and culturally sensitive to build rapport and foster collaboration within the virtual work environment. By adapting communication strategies to align with the client's culture, professionals can enhance productivity and achieve successful outcomes in online work relationships. Gudykunst and Kim (2003) emphasize the role of cultural empathy and adaptation in building successful intercultural relationships. In the increasingly globalized world of online work, it is essential for professionals to be sensitive to their clients' cultures in order to effectively communicate and collaborate. Cultural sensitivity encompasses understanding and respecting the values, norms, beliefs, and practices of different cultural groups. By acknowledging and adapting to a client's culture, professionals can build trust, show respect, and avoid misunderstandings that may arise due to cultural differences. This approach not only enhances communication but also fosters positive relationships with clients, leading to greater success in online work engagements. It is important for professionals to educate themselves on different cultures, remain open-minded, and be willing to adapt their approach as needed in order to achieve mutual understanding and effective collaboration with clients from diverse backgrounds. Hammer (2012) emphasizes the role of cultural sensitivity in fostering teamwork and synergy in multicultural environments.

Effects of self-confidence to participants' Communication with Clients. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are able to teach effectively, getting stuttered sometimes, easily caught up by students, affecting the delivery of ideas, and affecting speaking skills. This is how the research participants describe their struggles in the English language when it comes to self-confidence.

In the case of an ESL teacher, confidence plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of teaching. Without confidence in navigating online platforms, utilizing specialized technology, and engaging with students virtually, educators may struggle to convey information clearly

and effectively. The ability to adapt to virtual environments and confidently deliver content is essential for maintaining student engagement and participation. Instructors who lack confidence in their abilities to work online may come across as uncertain or unprepared, ultimately hindering the learning experience for their students. To ensure successful teaching in an online setting, it is imperative for educators to cultivate confidence through practice, training, and familiarization with digital tools and resources. Confident instructors are better equipped to engage learners, facilitate meaningful interactions, and deliver high-quality instruction in the ever-evolving landscape of online education. Artino (2012) highlights the impact of teacher confidence on communication effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

In the cases of those who work online, stuttering in doing their work as a result of low self-confidence can significantly impact an individual's professional performance and overall success. When someone lacks confidence in their abilities, they may struggle to effectively communicate with colleagues, clients, or supervisors through email, video calls, or written assignments. This can lead to misunderstandings, missed opportunities, and decreased productivity. Furthermore, stuttering while working online may further exacerbate feelings of inadequacy and increase anxiety levels, ultimately hindering one's ability to thrive in a competitive and fast-paced virtual work environment. Therefore, it is crucial for individuals experiencing this issue to seek support from mental health professionals or communication experts to address underlying self-esteem issues and develop strategies to boost self-confidence and improve their online performance. Manning (2016) emphasizes the importance of creating a safe and supportive atmosphere to help individuals with stuttering feel more confident and capable.

Students who struggle with low self-confidence may find it challenging to keep up with their work in an online environment. The lack of face-to-face interactions and immediate feedback can exacerbate feelings of inadequacy, leading to decreased motivation and productivity. Additionally, the pressure to perform well in a virtual setting can be overwhelming for students who already doubt their abilities. To address this issue, educators must take proactive steps to support students with low self-confidence by providing additional guidance, encouragement, and resources. It is crucial to create a positive and inclusive online learning environment where students feel safe to ask questions, seek help, and make mistakes without fear of judgment or failure. By fostering a sense of belonging and empowerment, educators can help students build their confidence and succeed academically in the digital realm. Deci and Ryan (2000) discuss the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in fostering intrinsic motivation and confidence. Low self-confidence can have a significant impact on the delivery of ideas when working online. Individuals who lack self-assurance may struggle to effectively communicate their thoughts and opinions, resulting in unclear or incomplete messages being conveyed. This can lead to misunderstandings, misinterpretations, and ultimately a decrease in productivity within a virtual work environment. Additionally, individuals with low self-esteem may hesitate to speak up during online meetings or discussions, missing out on valuable opportunities to contribute valuable insights and ideas. As a result, the overall quality of work produced may suffer, hindering the individual's ability to make a meaningful impact within their team or organization. It is crucial for individuals struggling with low self-confidence to address these feelings proactively through techniques such as therapy, self-care practices, and seeking support from colleagues or mentors to improve their confidence levels and enhance their ability to effectively deliver ideas in an online professional setting. Cashdan (2018) discusses how self-confidence influences assertiveness and communication effectiveness.

Coping Mechanisms When Struggling to Use English in Online Work. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are reading English books and watching movies, using chatgpt for grammar correction, and using google translate. This is how the research participants describe their coping mechanisms in their struggles in the English language.

Engaging in the practice of reading English books and watching movies can serve as an effective coping mechanism for individuals struggling with the demands of working online. By immersing oneself in literature and film, one can momentarily escape the pressures and stressors of remote work, allowing for a mental break and rejuvenation. Reading English books enhances cognitive abilities such as concentration, vocabulary expansion, and critical thinking skills, which can positively impact work performance. Similarly, watching movies provides a source of entertainment and relaxation that can alleviate tension and improve mood. Incorporating these activities into one's daily routine can promote mental well-being, increase productivity, and enhance overall job satisfaction amidst the challenges of remote work. Ultimately, engaging in these forms of media consumption not only serves as a means of distraction but also contributes to personal development and resilience in navigating the online work environment. Folkman and Moskowitz (2004) emphasize the importance of adaptive coping strategies that encompass a range of activities.

In today's digital age, many individuals rely on online platforms for work and communication, which can pose challenges in maintaining proper grammar and spelling. By leveraging advanced natural language processing tools such as ChatGPT for grammar correction and google translator, professionals can mitigate these issues and enhance the quality of their written content. Using ChatGPT and google translator as a coping mechanism allows individuals to streamline their workflow, improve efficiency, and ensure that their online interactions are professional and error-free. This innovative approach not only helps to alleviate the stress associated with struggling to produce high-quality written work but also empowers users to communicate effectively in various digital environments. Embracing technology like ChatGPT for grammar correction exemplifies a proactive response to the demands of modern-day remote work and reinforces the importance of continuous learning and adaptation in professional settings. Comas-Quinn (2011) explores the use of technology in language learning and its impact on inclusivity.

Ways of Adjusting to Negative Feedback in Using English. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are taking it positively, take it and study, remembering negative feedback, and not minding it. This is how the research participants describe their coping mechanisms in their struggles when they receive a negative feedback.

In the realm of online work, taking negative feedback positively and reflecting on it can serve as a valuable coping mechanism for individuals facing struggles. Instead of viewing criticism as a personal attack, workers can adopt a growth mindset and see it as an opportunity for improvement. By examining the feedback constructively, professionals can identify areas for development and make necessary adjustments to enhance their performance. This approach not only fosters self-improvement but also demonstrates resilience and adaptability in the face of challenges. Embracing negative feedback with an open mind enables individuals to cultivate stronger problem-solving skills, refine their work processes, and ultimately achieve greater success in the online sphere. By valuing critique as a tool for growth rather than a setback, workers can effectively navigate obstacles and thrive in their virtual endeavors. Stone and Heen (2014) explore strategies for receiving and utilizing feedback effectively.

As professionals navigating the challenges of working online, individuals often face negative feedback that can be discouraging and difficult to manage. However, adopting a mindset where they do not mind negative feedback can serve as an effective coping mechanism in overcoming these obstacles. By viewing negative feedback as an opportunity for growth and improvement rather than a personal attack, individuals can leverage criticism to enhance their skills and performance in their work. This resilience allows professionals to maintain confidence in their abilities and continue striving towards their goals despite setbacks. Embracing this approach can also foster a culture of continuous learning and development within online work environments, promoting higher levels of productivity and creativity. Ultimately, by reframing how they perceive and respond to criticism, individuals can bolster their adaptability and fortitude in the face of challenges while achieving greater success in their online endeavors. Masten (2011) discusses resilience as a dynamic process that involves adapting positively to adversity, which can include handling negative feedback.

Ways Used to Overcome Barriers of Communication Encountered. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are spending leisure time studying, through online checking, looking for translator, and read to learn more. This is how the research participants describe their coping mechanisms in their struggles when they experience barriers of communication.

In today's increasingly digital and virtual work environments, effective communication is crucial for success. By dedicating leisure time to studying and improving one's communication skills, individuals can overcome barriers that may arise when working online. Understanding different communication styles, being able to clearly articulate ideas and instructions, and actively listening to others are all essential components of effective online communication. Furthermore, investing time in studying non-verbal cues, tone of voice, and written communication etiquette can ensure that messages are conveyed accurately and understood correctly by colleagues or clients. By taking the initiative to enhance communication skills during leisure time, professionals can better navigate the complexities of remote work settings and ultimately boost their productivity and success in virtual collaborations. Langer (2014) states that Leisure-time studying fosters cognitive flexibility and problem-solving skills, enabling individuals to adapt to diverse communication challenges and find effective solutions.

Online checking is a crucial tool for overcoming communication barriers in remote work settings. By implementing regular online check-ins, team members can ensure that they are on the same page regarding project timelines, goals, and expectations. These regular meetings can help to clarify any misunderstandings or miscommunications that may arise in virtual collaborations. Additionally, online checking provides an opportunity for team members to provide updates on their progress, raise any concerns or obstacles they may be facing, and seek feedback or guidance from colleagues. This proactive approach to communication helps to build trust among team members, foster a sense of accountability, and ultimately lead to more efficient and successful outcomes in online work environments. Steinberg (2020) stated that Online checking tools save time by quickly identifying and correcting errors, allowing individuals to focus on content creation and communication rather than manual proofreading.

As the world becomes increasingly interconnected through online platforms, the need for efficient and accurate translation tools to overcome barriers of communication is paramount in professional settings. From collaborating with international colleagues to conducting business transactions with clients across different languages and cultures, a reliable translation tool can streamline workflow processes and enhance productivity. Tools such as Google Translate, DeepL, and Microsoft Translator offer real-time translations in various languages, allowing professionals to communicate effectively and accurately without language barriers. Additionally, these tools provide nuanced translations that take into account context and cultural nuances, ensuring that messages are conveyed appropriately. Investing in a high-quality translation tool not only enhances collaboration but also demonstrates a commitment to inclusivity and global communication in the workplace. Goggin et al. (2018) stated that translation tools support multilingual communication by enabling seamless translation between languages, promoting inclusivity and understanding in diverse teams.

Working Out Differences Between Own and Clients Culture. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are considered other culture, think of client's side, adjust to students, learn to read and watch movies, and be mindful and learning other culture. This is how the research participants describe their coping mechanisms in their struggles when they experience difference in culture.

In order to effectively overcome cultural barriers when working online, it is imperative to consider and respect the value systems, customs, communication styles, and working practices of other cultures. By taking the time to understand the nuances of different cultures, individuals can build stronger relationships with colleagues and clients from diverse backgrounds. This can lead to improved collaboration, productivity, and ultimately success in a globalized work environment. It is important to be open-minded, adaptable, and willing to learn from others in order to bridge cultural divides and work effectively together online. By embracing diversity and inclusivity, individuals can harness the strengths of multiple perspectives and create a more inclusive and harmonious virtual work environment. Ultimately, by considering other cultures when working online, individuals can break down barriers and foster a more cohesive global community. Du-Babcock et al. (2020) expressed that virtual cultural competence refers to the ability to navigate cultural differences effectively in online and virtual work environments. It involves leveraging technology for cross-cultural collaboration while respecting cultural diversity.

In the case of the ESL teacher, in order to effectively adjust to students and overcome cultural barriers in online work environments, it is essential for educators to cultivate a deep understanding of diverse cultural norms and practices. By recognizing the unique perspectives and experiences of each student, instructors can tailor their teaching methods and communication strategies to create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. This may involve implementing culturally-relevant examples, providing additional resources for non-native English speakers, or encouraging open discussions about cultural differences in order to foster mutual respect and understanding among students. Additionally, utilizing technology that supports multiple languages, incorporating virtual collaboration tools that accommodate various communication styles, and offering flexible assessment options can further enhance the online learning experience for all students. By actively addressing cultural barriers through thoughtful adaptation and consideration, educators can empower students from different backgrounds to thrive academically and professionally in a digital world. Hammer and Bennett (2001) highlighted that cultural sensitivity involves understanding and respecting students' cultural backgrounds, beliefs, values, communication styles, and learning preferences.

In order to effectively overcome cultural barriers in online work environments, it is essential to broaden one's understanding of different cultures. One effective way to achieve this is by reading books and watching movies that provide insights into various cultural norms, values, and practices. By immersing oneself in the narratives and perspectives of different cultures, individuals can gain a deeper appreciation for the diversity that exists within our global society. This not only enhances cross-cultural communication skills but also fosters a sense of empathy and respect for individuals from different backgrounds. Additionally, exposure to different cultural perspectives through literature and film can help develop critical thinking skills and facilitate more inclusive and collaborative work environments. Ultimately, leveraging these resources can empower individuals to navigate cultural differences with confidence and sensitivity in the digital workspace. Shuter (2012) stated that reading and watching media from other cultures provide a form of cultural immersion, allowing individuals to experience different customs, traditions, values, and social norms firsthand.

In today's increasingly globalized world, the ability to understand and appreciate different cultures has become essential for success in online work environments. By taking the time to learn about the cultural norms, communication styles, and business practices of other countries, individuals can overcome cultural barriers and build strong working relationships with colleagues from around the world. This not only helps in fostering mutual respect and trust but also enhances collaboration and productivity. Learning about different cultures can also provide valuable insights into new perspectives and approaches that can be applied to problem-solving and decision-making processes. Ultimately, embracing diversity and cultural awareness in online work settings can lead to more efficient and inclusive teamwork, ultimately driving success in a globalized marketplace. Matsumoto and Hwang (2013) stated that interpersonal sensitivity refers to the ability to understand and respond appropriately to the feelings, thoughts, and behaviors of others, including those from different cultural backgrounds.

Ways Used to Boost Self-confidence Using English Language. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are using freetime reading books and watching movies, doing practice often times, and studying in advance books. This is how the research participants describe their coping mechanisms in their struggles in their self-confidence.

Utilizing free time to engage in reading books and watching movies can significantly boost confidence when completing work online. The act of reading books allows individuals to broaden their knowledge, enhance critical thinking skills, and improve comprehension abilities. This can translate into improved problem-solving skills and a more efficient approach to tasks and projects. Additionally, watching movies provides a unique opportunity for visual learning, allowing individuals to absorb information in a different format than traditional textual resources. By exploring diverse genres and themes through both mediums, individuals can gain new perspectives, cultivate creativity, and develop a well-rounded skill set that is essential for success in an online work environment. Overall, investing time in these activities not only enhances job performance but also instills a sense of confidence and competence when navigating the digital workspace. Robbins (2014) stated that reading books and watching movies can expand knowledge in various areas, including professional skills, industry trends, leadership, and communication, which can contribute to increased confidence in online work.

Consistent practice is essential for improving confidence in performing tasks online. By dedicating time regularly to honing one's skills and familiarizing oneself with various tools and platforms, individuals can build competence and efficiency in their work. This continuous practice not only enhances technical proficiency but also helps individuals feel more comfortable navigating the digital

landscape, resulting in increased self-assurance and reduced apprehension when facing new challenges. Moreover, frequent practice allows for greater adaptability and problem-solving abilities, enabling professionals to respond effectively to unforeseen circumstances or changes in the online environment. Overall, investing time and effort into repetitive practice can significantly boost confidence levels, equipping individuals with the necessary skills and mindset to excel in their online endeavors. Hayes (2019) stated that regular practice helps reduce anxiety and apprehension related to online work tasks, as individuals become more skilled, prepared, and confident in their abilities to tackle challenges effectively.

Studying in advance by reading books to boost confidence in doing work online is essential for professional growth and success. By immersing oneself in literature that covers topics such as digital marketing, project management, technical skills, or industry-specific knowledge, individuals can familiarize themselves with best practices and stay ahead of the curve. This proactive approach helps build a strong foundation of knowledge, enabling individuals to approach their online work with confidence and expertise. Additionally, studying in advance allows individuals to anticipate challenges, problem-solve effectively, and take on complex tasks with ease. As technology continues to evolve rapidly, staying informed through targeted reading not only boosts confidence but also enhances one's overall performance and credibility in the digital realm. Ultimately, investing time in reading resources not only prepares professionals for current projects but also equips them for future opportunities in the constantly changing digital landscape. Brown (2018) stated that studying in advance allows individuals to anticipate challenges, risks, and potential issues in online work, enabling them to develop strategies, contingency plans, and solutions proactively, which boosts confidence in handling uncertainties.

Simple Routines Used in Everyday Work to Develop Communication Skills. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are watching movies, reading, little conversation before the class, read, listen and practice speaking, and reading simple instruction. This is how the research participant shared their insights in their simple routines to develop their usage and learning of the English language.

Watching movies as a simple routine to develop communication skills can be an effective method for individuals looking to enhance their ability to connect and engage with others. By regularly observing and analyzing various types of dialogue, body language, and emotions portrayed on screen, viewers can improve their own communication techniques. Paying attention to how characters convey information, express emotions, and navigate interpersonal relationships can serve as a valuable learning experience that can be applied in real-life interactions. Additionally, exposure to different genres of films can broaden one's understanding of diverse communication styles and perspectives. Moreover, watching movies with subtitles or in a foreign language can also help individuals become more comfortable with listening comprehension and expand their vocabulary. Ultimately, incorporating movie watching into one's routine for developing communication skills is a practical and enjoyable way to sharpen verbal and non-verbal communication abilities. Wood (2016) stated explained that movies showcase a wide range of verbal communication, such as dialogues, speeches, negotiations, and debates, as well as nonverbal communication cues like body language, tone of voice, and facial expressions, which are crucial for effective communication.

Reading is an essential and straightforward routine that can significantly enhance communication skills in individuals. By regularly engaging with a variety of written materials, such as books, articles, reports, and even social media posts, individuals can expand their vocabulary, improve their sentence structure, and learn how to effectively convey their thoughts and ideas. Reading allows one to observe different writing styles, tone, and techniques which can be applied in their verbal or written communication. Additionally, by reading a diverse range of content on various subjects, individuals can broaden their knowledge base which will enable them to engage in meaningful conversations with others. Therefore, incorporating reading into one's daily routine is not only fundamental for personal development but also plays a crucial role in enhancing professional communication skills. Nation (2001) stated that Reading exposes individuals to a wide range of words, phrases, and expressions, leading to vocabulary expansion and improved language proficiency, which are essential for effective communication.

Beginning class with a brief conversation can have numerous benefits for students in terms of developing their communication skills. By engaging in small talk before the lesson begins, students have the opportunity to practice initiating and maintaining a conversation in a relaxed setting. This routine can help them feel more comfortable speaking up during class discussions, sharing their ideas with classmates, and asking questions when they need clarification. Additionally, this practice encourages active listening and empathy as students learn to show interest in others' opinions and experiences. Over time, these simple interactions can build confidence in their ability to communicate effectively both inside and outside the classroom, ultimately preparing them for success in their future careers where strong communication skills are essential. Tannen (1994) stated that engaging in pre-class conversations encourages active participation, collaboration, and exchange of ideas among classmates, contributing to a vibrant learning environment and enhanced communication skills.

Developing strong communication skills is essential in any professional setting. By incorporating a routine of reading, listening, and practicing speaking, individuals can greatly enhance their ability to effectively communicate with colleagues, clients, and superiors. Reading allows individuals to expand their vocabulary and knowledge base, keeping them up-to-date on industry trends and advancements. Listening plays a crucial role in understanding the viewpoints and concerns of others, fostering empathy and building stronger interpersonal relationships. Finally, practicing speaking helps individuals articulate their thoughts clearly and confidently when presenting ideas or engaging in discussions. By making this routine a regular part of one's professional development strategy,

individuals can improve their communication skills over time and ultimately enhance their success in the workplace. Lightbown and Spada (2013) stated that Incorporating reading, listening, and speaking practice provides a comprehensive approach to language acquisition and communication skill development.

Reading simple instructions may seem mundane, but in reality, it is a crucial routine for developing effective communication skills. By carefully following written directions, individuals can enhance their reading comprehension and critical thinking abilities. Additionally, practicing this skill consistently will improve attention to detail and the ability to accurately interpret information. Furthermore, mastering the art of reading instructions lays a solid foundation for effective written and verbal communication in professional settings. Employers value employees who can follow directions accurately, as it demonstrates dependability and reliability. Ultimately, by treating reading simple instructions as a simple routine, individuals can strengthen their communication skills and set themselves apart in the workplace. Pinker (2014) stated that effective instructional writing requires clear communication, consideration of the audience's needs and background knowledge, and the ability to convey information accurately and comprehensibly.

Advice to Students on the Importance of Learning English Language. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are be more capable in English, practice English at home, need to study English fluently, and learn and listen everywhere. This is how the research participants shared their advice to students on the importance of learning the English language.

Practicing English at home as a daily routine is an essential method to enhance communication skills. Incorporating language practice into one's daily schedule provides a structured and consistent approach towards achieving fluency. By engaging in activities such as reading, listening to podcasts, or conversing with native speakers, individuals can fine-tune their grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation. Furthermore, regularly practicing English at home encourages confidence and proficiency in speaking the language effectively in professional settings. Consistency is key when it comes to language acquisition, and establishing a routine for English practice ensures steady progress over time. Ultimately, dedicating time each day to improve one's communication skills will not only benefit personal development but also open up new opportunities for career advancement and success in various professional endeavors. Richards and Schmidt (2010) stated that regular practice at home helps improve language fluency, pronunciation, intonation, and overall proficiency in English communication.

In order to enhance communication skills, it is imperative to adopt a routine of learning and listening in various settings. By exposing oneself to diverse environments and actively engaging in conversations with individuals from different backgrounds, one can refine their ability to articulate thoughts clearly and effectively. This routine should include seeking out opportunities to participate in networking events, attending professional development workshops, and actively listening to podcasts or audiobooks that cover a wide range of topics. Additionally, practicing active listening skills, such as maintaining eye contact, asking thoughtful questions, and paraphrasing what others have said, can greatly improve one's ability to communicate with clarity and empathy. Overall, incorporating learning and listening into daily routines will undoubtedly contribute to the development of strong communication skills necessary for success in any professional setting. Bodie (2011) stated that active listening has been shown to enhance interpersonal relationships and communication effectiveness. He added further that practice active listening by fully concentrating, understanding, and responding to what is being said. This not only improves your ability to understand others but also demonstrates respect and empathy.

Lessons Learned from Experiences in Using English Language Efficiently. This structured theme summarizes the views of the five online workers. The emerging themes are need to consider other culture, consider receivers accent, being good in enunciating words, being confident enough, keep practicing, need to study more phonics, importance of little things to learn difficult one, and develop learning inside and outside the school. This is how the research participants shared the lessons they have learned in their experiences and struggles using the English language.

In today's increasingly globalized world, it is essential for professionals to recognize the significance of understanding and respecting other cultures as a means of developing effective communication skills. By actively engaging with individuals from diverse cultural backgrounds, professionals gain valuable insights into differing communication styles, norms, and behaviors. This exposure not only fosters greater empathy and sensitivity towards others but also enhances one's ability to adapt their communication approach accordingly. In doing so, professionals can mitigate misunderstandings, build stronger interpersonal relationships, and ultimately improve overall productivity and performance in cross-cultural environments. Embracing cultural diversity as a lesson in communication development not only enriches one's personal growth but also contributes to fostering inclusive work environments that celebrate differences and promote collaboration across borders. A research by Deardorff (2006) shows that immersive cultural experiences are highly effective in developing intercultural competence. It shows that if possible, immerse yourself in different cultural settings, either through travel, community events, or virtual exchanges. Experiencing other cultures firsthand can significantly enhance your communication skills.

In a professional setting, it is essential to consider the receiver's accent as a valuable lesson in developing effective communication skills. By paying attention to the accent of the person you are communicating with, you demonstrate respect for their background and cultural differences. This level of awareness can lead to improved understanding and collaboration, ultimately enhancing productivity and fostering positive relationships in the workplace. Additionally, taking the time to adjust your own speaking pace and tone to accommodate a different accent can help bridge potential communication gaps and ensure that all parties involved are on the same

page. Ultimately, by acknowledging and embracing diversity in accents, professionals can cultivate a more inclusive and culturally competent work environment. Lindemann (2002) found that speakers who adjust their speech to accommodate non-native accents improve communication clarity and mutual understanding. He explained that when communicating with someone with a strong accent, speak clearly and at a moderate pace. Avoid using slang or idiomatic expressions that might be unfamiliar.

Being good in enunciating words is crucial for developing strong communication skills in professional settings. Clear and articulate speech enhances the effectiveness of your message and demonstrates professionalism and confidence to your audience. Enunciating words accurately helps ensure that your message is understood correctly, reducing the likelihood of miscommunication or confusion. Furthermore, practicing proper enunciation can improve your overall speaking abilities, such as pronunciation, tone, and pacing. It also conveys a sense of respect towards your listeners by showing that you have taken the time to speak clearly and thoughtfully. Developing this skill not only boosts your communication capabilities but also enhances your credibility and authority in the workplace. In conclusion, mastering enunciation is an essential lesson for professionals looking to excel in their careers by effectively communicating with colleagues, clients, and stakeholders. According to a study by Boersma and Weenink (2001), regular practice of articulation exercises can significantly enhance speech clarity and intelligibility.

Confidence is essential in the development of effective communication skills. When individuals are confident in themselves and their abilities, they are better able to convey their thoughts and ideas clearly and assertively. Confidence enables individuals to speak up in meetings, present their viewpoints persuasively, and engage in productive discussions with colleagues and clients. This self-assurance also helps individuals project credibility and expertise in their interactions, leading to greater trust and respect from others. Developing confidence as a lesson in communication skills allows professionals to navigate challenging situations with ease and successfully build relationships both inside and outside of the workplace. By prioritizing confidence-building exercises and practice, individuals can enhance their communication skills and achieve greater success in their careers. A research by Todd et al. (2014) suggests that positive self-talk can enhance performance and reduce anxiety in stressful situations.

In the professional realm, consistently practicing and honing communication skills is imperative for success. Effective communication is a cornerstone of building relationships with colleagues, clients, and stakeholders. By making a concerted effort to practice and refine communication techniques, professionals can articulate thoughts clearly, engage in active listening, and convey information in a concise and coherent manner. Through ongoing practice, individuals can increase their confidence in expressing ideas, resolving conflicts diplomatically, and delivering presentations with impact. Additionally, regularly practicing communication skills can help professionals adapt to different communication styles and navigate diverse workplace dynamics effectively. In essence, treating communication as a skill that requires continual refinement through practice is essential for fostering strong professional relationships and achieving career objectives. Hattie and Timperley (2007) emphasize the importance of feedback in learning, noting that it significantly enhances performance and skill development. They stated that you can request constructive feedback from peers, mentors, or communication coaches as feedback provides insights into areas of improvement and helps refine your skills.

In the professional world, mastering communication skills is crucial for success in any industry. One effective way to improve these skills is by paying attention to the little things. By focusing on smaller, more manageable tasks and gradually working towards larger ones, individuals can develop a solid foundation of communication techniques. For example, practicing active listening during meetings or presentations can significantly enhance one's ability to understand and respond appropriately in various professional settings. Additionally, learning how to effectively communicate through written correspondence, such as emails or reports, can greatly impact an individual's success in conveying information clearly and concisely. Ultimately, recognizing the importance of honing these small details as stepping stones to mastering more complex communication challenges can lead to significant improvements in professional relationships and overall effectiveness in the workplace. Bandura (1997) discusses how taking incremental steps and achieving small successes can enhance self-efficacy and motivation.

Effective communication skills are a crucial component of success in both professional and personal realms. By incorporating opportunities for learning inside and outside the school environment, students can develop these vital skills early on. Inside the school, formal classroom settings can provide structured learning experiences such as debates, presentations, and group projects that require effective communication. Additionally, extracurricular activities like public speaking clubs or theater programs offer a platform for students to hone their communication abilities in a less conventional setting. Both environments present unique challenges that help students refine their verbal, nonverbal, and written communication techniques. By actively engaging in various learning opportunities inside and outside the school, students are better equipped to navigate complex interpersonal interactions and effectively convey their thoughts and ideas in professional settings later on. Moreover, internships and work experiences are critical for bridging the gap between academic learning and practical application, enhancing employability and communication skills (Duey et al., 2010).

Conclusions

English is considered the world's lingua franca, meaning it is the most widely spoken language across the globe. As such, the importance of learning English cannot be overstated. In today's interconnected world, English proficiency opens doors to a wide range of opportunities both professionally and personally. Many international businesses require employees to have a strong command of English in order to communicate effectively with colleagues and clients from different countries. By mastering the English language, individuals are able to participate in global discussions, access a wealth of information online, and expand their horizons beyond their

own communities.

Furthermore, learning English enhances cultural understanding and promotes tolerance. Language is not just a means of communication; it is also a reflection of culture and history. By learning English, individuals gain insight into the customs, traditions, and values of English-speaking countries. This cultural exchange fosters empathy and respect for diversity, helping to bridge gaps between people from different backgrounds. In a world that is increasingly interconnected, the ability to communicate in English can facilitate meaningful cross-cultural interactions and promote dialogue between individuals from diverse backgrounds.

Moreover, proficiency in English is essential for academic advancement and intellectual growth. Many of the world's top universities teach courses in English, and academic publications are often written in English. By mastering the language, students gain access to a wealth of knowledge and research that can further their education and enhance their critical thinking skills. In conclusion, the importance of learning English cannot be underestimated, as it opens doors to a myriad of opportunities, promotes cultural understanding, and enhances academic and intellectual growth.

In as much as the study was limited to the responses of the participants who work online as online math tutor, virtual assistant, ESL teacher, call center agent, and cybora, the following implications for future research are considered:

First, future research may be conducted by selecting other group of online workers with different cases. Second, another research of the same focus may be conducted to other alumni from other schools to explore and discover the same cases on examining the English proficiency of online workers.

Finally, the findings of the study are viewed from the lens of the selected workers online from Mt. Diwata High School research participants and informants. Another research could be conducted to find out the experiences, struggles, coping mechanisms, and insights of workers in different field regarding the importance of their learning on the English language inside and outside the school.

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